

Regression Analysis of Heart Rate to Indicate Driving Fatigue using Design Expert Software

Muhammad Shafiq Ibrahim¹, Seri Rahayu Kamat^{1*}, Syamimi Shamsuddin¹, Minoru Fukumi²

¹Fakulti Kejuruteraan Pembuatan, Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM), 76100 Durian Tunggal, Melaka, Malaysia

²Department of Information Science and Intelligent System, Faculty of Engineering, University of Tokushima, 770-8506 Minamijosanjima-Cho, Tokushima, Japan

*Corresponding author email: seri@utem.edu.my

Abstract

Malaysia, like many other countries, has seen an increase in the frequency of fatigue-related road accidents. To avoid road accidents, a reliable indicator to detect driving fatigue is critically needed. This study aims to conduct a regression analysis to establish whether input factors, namely (i) age, (ii) driving duration, (iii) body mass index (BMI), (iv) gender and (v) types of roads are significant in affecting the heart rate and how these factors interact to indicate driving fatigue. The regression analysis utilized Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) by Design Expert software. The ANOVA revealed that the values of Prob > F for all variables were less than 0.01%, showing that all factors have an impact on heart rate. Because of the release of adrenaline in reaction to a stressful occurrence while driving, the heart rate decreases as age increases. The heart rate increases as the driving duration increases for the same reason. Meanwhile, the heart rate increases as BMI rises due to obesity-related health conditions. However, the heart rate reduces as gender shifts from female to male and road geometry shifts from winding to monotonous due to sex hormone differences and physiological signatures of boredom generated by road geometry respectively. The regression model was verified in order to determine its reliability in predicting heart rate. The investigation exhibited exceptional prediction accuracy, with the model capable of predicting the output data within a 95% predictive interval, meeting the minimum quantitative criteria of a 90% predictive interval. Furthermore, the residual errors were less than 10%, indicating that the model is very accurate in forecasting heart rate. The regression analysis is likely to be valuable in guiding academics and policymakers in the field of road safety to reduce traffic accidents caused by driving fatigue.

Keywords: Driver fatigue, regression analysis, heart rate, Design Expert software

1. Introduction

Malaysia is constantly urbanizing and has become one of the most densely populated countries in Southeast Asia. Malaysia's urban population has increased substantially from 70% in 2010 to 77% in 2020 and is expected to exceed 80% by 2030. Due to increased commuting durations and distances due to urbanization, there is a high rate of car ownership. This is consistent with Malaysia's dramatic increase in the number of registered automobiles from 3,447,712 units in 1996 to 17,486,589 units in 2020 (CEIC, 2021). However, increasing urban mobility does lead to a significant increase in traffic accident. According to the Malaysian Institute of Road Safety Research (MIROS), the number of road accidents in Malaysia has risen from 414,421 in 2010 to 567,516 in 2019 (MIROS, 2021). Due to the deployment of movement control orders (MCO) during the COVID-19 pandemic, the statistic was significantly reduced in 2020 to 418,245 occurrences (MIROS, 2021).

Slow reaction times, lack of awareness and improper information processing as a result of driving fatigue are the primary causes of road accidents (Li et al., 2020). Driver fatigue is defined as a condition of extreme tiredness or exhaustion caused by a decline in one's mental and physical capacities while operating a vehicle. To prevent fatigue-related road accidents, the parameter to indicate driving fatigue and factors affecting the parameter must be identified and studied.

A study of the current literature found that only a few attempts have been made so far to investigate the effects of human physiological systems such as heart rate in indicating driving fatigue. Driving a car is a complex task that requires the interaction of several fundamental cognitive abilities, including memory, attention, decision-making and motor skills (Ibrahim et al., 2022). People with faster heart rate levels have a finer ability to manage and repress unpleasant memories (Gillie et al., 2014). Meanwhile, a lower heart rate is associated with worse performance in both short and long-term verbal memory (Frewen et al., 2013). Several sleep laboratory investigations suggest that heart rate can be a reliable predictor of vigilant state assessed by reaction speed to visual stimuli during whole (Chua et al., 2012) and partial sleep loss (Henelius et al., 2014). Heart rate has also been linked to cognitive task load and duration spent on task (Hidalgo-Muñoz et al., 2018). With the advancement of unobtrusive sensing methods, heart rate could be recorded in daily driving scenarios using wearable sensors (Sikander & Anwar, 2018) or car-integrated sensors (Leonhardt et al., 2018). As a result, it is acceptable to assume that heart rate can be a reliable indicator of driving fatigue.

Hence, the study aims to determine which factors, namely (i) age, (ii) driving duration, (iii) body mass index (BMI), (iv) gender and (v) types of roads are significant in affecting the heart rate and how these variables affect each other in indicating driving fatigue using regression analysis by Design Expert software.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Factors that Influence Driver's Performance

2.1.1. Age

Young drivers have significantly contributed to road accidents globally. Researchers used the phrase "young drivers" to refer to those aged 18 to 24 (Mohamad, 2017). Various traffic offences, such as drunk driving, failure to wear a seatbelt, sudden lane changes, texting while driving and speeding, could be assigned to the young driver (Leandro, 2012). However, among these offences, speeding is considered the most common and severe by young drivers. According to earlier research, motivational factors have profoundly encouraged young male drivers to go beyond the speed limit, despite modest advances in driving skills (Ferguson et al., 2007). As a result, they contributed three to four times as many accidents as any other older or more experienced motorist (Clarke et al., 2010). A study found that, crash rates among ages of 20-25 years old are more than twice as high as those among aged 30-34 (Arnett, 2002).

2.1.2. Driving duration

Stressful events while driving might trigger an acute stress response, impairing essential physiological systems (Magaña et al., 2020). The longer the driving period, the more likely it is that stressful driving events, such as maintaining a constant speed, braking and pulling away at traffic lights or simply sitting in traffic, will occur. Firdaus et al. (2017) found that 15 to 30 minutes of driving is sufficient to affect the muscles while driving, hence causing fatigue. These stressful events can lead to repeated decreases in heart rate which cause rises in blood pressure. These fluctuations are the major risk factors for developing high blood pressure (hypertension). Ani et al. (2017) discovered that when the driving time increased from 15 to 30 minutes, the average heart rate decreased from 110 to 89 beats per minute.

2.1.3. Body mass index (BMI)

Studies suggest that when BMI rises, so does the risk of developing physiological system failure, such as cardiovascular disease (CD). Obese patients' blood volume and cardiac output rise in response to the need to perfuse greater mass as well as higher baseline oxygen demand (Stelfox et al., 2006). However, a person with a high BMI is at a higher risk of developing cardiovascular disorders such as hypertension (high blood pressure), coronary artery disease (CAD), stroke and heart failure (Elagizi et al., 2018). Haslam and James (2005) and Lavie et al. (2018) support this finding as the prevalence of modifiable risk factors for atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD), such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and dyslipidemia, is higher in overweight and obese people. Wang et al. (2010) studied the interactions between blood pressure and BMI in relation to cardiovascular disease and discovered that the impact of systolic or diastolic blood pressure on the risk of cardiovascular disease increased with increasing BMI levels (underweight, normal, overweight, and obese).

2.1.4. Gender

Male and female anatomical and physiological differences are thought to cause differences in human performance limits. Body composition disparities between men and women are widely known: men typically have more muscle mass, more bone mass and a lower percentage of body fat than women (Blair, 2007). These differences alter the structural or morphological structure of many (if not all) organ systems in adult males and females, which can have a substantial impact on physiological function (Legato and Bilezikian, 2004). For instance, gender disparities in lung size have significant implications. Even when height is taken into account, men have bigger lungs, wider airways and better lung diffusion capacity than women which is beneficial for oxygen transportation (Harms, 2006).

2.1.5. Types of roads

A few studies have pointed out few types of road geometry that have effect on driver's performance, namely (i) monotonous and (ii) winding. Monotony driving is described as long motorway rides (Larue et al., 2011), in light traffic, with few curves, consistent noise levels and monotonous landscapes (May and Baldwin, 2009). When subjected to monotony, the human central nervous system suffers a reduction in the amount of cerebral activation, which manifests as feelings of fatigue, sleepiness, decreased attention, disinterest in the work and decline in attentiveness (Larue et al., 2010). A winding road is a condition where there are three or more curves in it that are separated by a tangent distance of less than 600 feet (Milstead et al., 2011). According to statistical assessments of

traffic accidents on Japanese motorways, the occurrence ratio of false-perception accidents is higher on curved roads than on straight roads in cases when the driver is the primary cause of the accident (Yotsutsuji et al., 2017).

3. Methodology

3.1. Demographic Data

The selection of respondents was based on three factors, (i) Age: 20-25 years old and 30-35 years old (ii) BMI: healthy (18.5-24.9 kg/m²), overweight (25.0-29.9 kg/m²) and obese (30 kg/m² and above) and (iii) gender: female and male. As a result, six female and six male respondents were chosen to reflect these variables. All respondents, regardless of BMI, were free of both short- and long-term diseases and did not require daily medication.

3.2. Experimental Design

First, anthropometry measurements were taken like height and weight to confirm the respondent's BMI. To guarantee that the baseline fatigue in all respondents was comparable, the respondents were instructed to get at least seven to nine hours of adequate sleep the night before the road test. Sleep deprivation can result from a lack of sleep, which increases the chance of falling asleep while driving. Drivers who do not get sufficient sleep may develop hypertension, which may impair their capacity to drive. Before the experiment, each respondent's blood pressure was measured with an Omron Evolv to ensure that it was within normal limits of 80 mm Hg for the diastolic and 120 mm Hg for the systolic. The individuals were also prohibited from ingesting alcohol or caffeine-containing beverages for seven hours before the experiment. Figure 1 shows the experimental flow.

Figure 1: Experimental flow

Driver fatigue is most likely in the early morning 2.00 a.m. to 6.00 a.m. and early afternoon 2.00 p.m. to 4.00 p.m. These are the moments when the biological clock naturally dips, causing tiredness and decreased concentration. To guarantee that all respondents are fit to drive, the driving test was done on real-world roads between 9.00 a.m. and 12.00 p.m., when there have been minimal reports of fatigue-related traffic incidents (Di Milia et al., 2011). The vehicle was a Perodua Bezza GA T with an automatic transmission. The entire experiment was carried out on sunny days and radio and cell phone use while driving was restricted. The heart rate was measured by inserting a wireless pulse oximeter on the participant's fingertip. The measurements were taken both before and after the driving test. The details of experimental design (independent variables) were summarized as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Design summary of experimental design (input factor)

	Minimum	Maximum	Unit
Numeric Variable			
Age	20	35	years old
Driving Duration	15.00	30.00	minute
BMI	18.50	30.00	kg/m ²
Qualitative Variable			
Gender	Female	Male	-
Road Types	Winding	Monotonous	-

3.3. Regression Analysis

A regression analysis technique by Design Expert software was used since it has been shown to be effective in determining potential interactions between two or more variables. The statistical analysis technique namely Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was carried out by this software. First, the experimental run table was created based on the experimental design of input factors as shown in Table 1. Sixty-eight experimental runs were carried out in this study. The experimental run table was developed by the Design Expert software based on the minimum and maximum value of each input factor. The heart rate (output response) data gathered from real-road driving experiments was then loaded into the experimental run table. The model was then examined using ANOVA to identify whether input factors are significant in influencing heart rate and how input factors and output response influence each other in indicating driving fatigue. Finally, the polynomial equation that forecasted the value of the output response was constructed for model validation purposes.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

The ANOVA was used to anticipate which input factors were significant in influencing the output response and to describe how the input variables were significant in influencing the output response. The chance that the null hypothesis of the entire regression model was true was represented by the Prob>F value. If the Prob>F value was below 0.01 percent, the model had a substantial impact on the output response. According to Table 2, the model was significant because the sum of squares value of 5219.86 was less than 0.01%.

Table 2 demonstrates that the Prob>F values for A= Age, B= Driving Duration, C= BMI, D= Gender and E= Types of Roads were below 0.01 %, showing that the input factors influenced the heart rate significantly. Driving duration was the most significant factor that affected heart rate, with a Prob>F value of B² was also below 0.01%. The next sections describe the behavior of the heart rate acquired by software prediction and real-road driving experiment in response to the significant input factors.

Table 2: ANOVA analysis

Source	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F Value	Prob > F
Model	5219.86	18	289.99	89.82	< 0.0001
A	1273.47	1	1273.47	394.45	< 0.0001
B	1275.12	1	1275.12	394.96	< 0.0001
C	952.74	1	952.74	295.10	< 0.0001
D	695.37	1	695.37	215.38	< 0.0001
E	496.03	1	496.03	153.64	< 0.0001
A2	1.78	1	1.78	0.55	0.4614
B2	262.25	1	262.25	81.23	< 0.0001
C2	3.41	1	3.41	1.06	0.3091
AB	0.36	1	0.36	0.11	0.7386
AC	9.00	1	9.00	2.79	0.1014
AD	0.50	1	0.50	0.15	0.6956
AE	0.50	1	0.50	0.15	0.6956
BC	0.57	1	0.57	0.18	0.6767
BD	6.35	1	6.35	1.97	0.1671
BE	7.40	1	7.40	2.29	0.1366
CD	0.50	1	0.50	0.15	0.6956
CE	2.00	1	2.00	0.62	0.4350
DE	2.12	1	2.12	0.66	0.4219
Residual	158.20	49	3.23		
Lack of Fit	108.20	33	3.28	1.05	0.4762
Pure Error	50.00	16	3.13		
Cor Total	5378.06	67			

4.1.1. Age

Figure 2a shows the decrease in heart rate for software prediction and real-road driving experiment as age increased from 20 to 30 years. The findings could be attributed to age-related differences in stress management.

Driving is a stressful activity that entails a series of high-risk and unpredictable events, such as driving during rush hour, getting stopped in traffic and feeling out of control. The heart rate responds to stress, according to studies (Steiner et al., 2002). A study compared heart rate reactivity to stressful and non-stressful events and found that the heart rate was considerably higher in stressful situations (Dobkin and Pihl, 1992). In such situations, the human body releases adrenaline, a hormone that temporarily raises the heart rate to stimulate the inefficient heart to perform harder. Figure 2a demonstrates that young drivers had a greater heart rate, indicating that they were under a lot more stress compared to senior drivers. The outcome is consistent with a study, as senior drivers reported significantly less stress than younger drivers. Physiological evidence shows that elderly drivers may underestimate their driving stress (Zhao et al., 2020). According to studies, young drivers are more likely to be impacted by their surroundings while driving, resulting in a succession of stress emotions that impair their cognition, attention, judgement and behavior, leading to unsafe driving. As a result, youthful drivers account for the majority of traffic incidents (Kadoya et al., 2021; Steinhauser et al., 2018).

4.1.2. Driving duration

Figure 2b shows that the heart rate went up for both techniques as the driving time increased from 15 to 30 minutes. The adrenaline released by stressful driving scenarios could explain the pattern. Driving is a stressful activity that involves a succession of high-risk and unpredictable occurrences, such as driving during rush hour, sitting in traffic, and keeping a constant pace in one's lane. Therefore, spending long periods of time behind the wheel causes a stress response over time (Antoun et al., 2017). According to research (Steiner et al., 2002), the heart rate responds to stress. A study looked at heart rate reactivity in reaction to stressful and non-stressful events and discovered that the heart rate was significantly greater in stressful situations (Dobkin and Pihl, 1992). In such cases, the human body releases adrenaline, a hormone that causes the heart rate to momentarily increase in order to encourage the inefficient heart to work harder. As a result, the stress caused by long durations of driving has a considerable impact on the heart rate.

4.1.3. Body mass index (BMI)

Figure 2c displays the increase in heart rate obtained by software prediction and real-road driving experiments when BMI climbed from 18.50 kg/m² (healthy) to 30.00 kg/m² (obesity). This finding could be linked to an obesity-related health issue. A person with a BMI of 30 kg/m² or more (obesity) is more prone to suffering from atrial fibrillation, a rapid and irregular heartbeat. According to the study (Foy, 2018), obese adults had a 40% higher risk of developing atrial fibrillation than healthy ones. The findings are consistent with prior research, which found that obese people have a higher heart rate than normal-BMI adults (Frank et al., 1986). Excess fatty substances accumulate in the arteries of obese people, making the heart pump harder to deliver blood throughout the body, causing the heart to beat quicker. The increase in heart rate caused by nervous system stimulation creates high blood pressure on the inner walls of the arteries, resulting in hypertension. Obese long-distance truck drivers, according to one study (Rike et al., 2022), are more likely to develop hypertension than normal people.

Figure 2: Interaction between input variable and output response (a) age; (b) driving duration; (c) BMI; (d) gender; (e) types of roads

4.1.4. Gender

Figure 2d depicts the reduction in heart rate obtained through software prediction and actual driving experiments when female drivers were substituted with male drivers. The difference in sex hormones could explain the drop in heart rate. Stressful jobs, such as driving a car, are handled differently by men and women. Driving necessitates a high degree of cognitive skills such as working memory, decision making, and cognitive flexibility, which can lead to stress. Stressful life situations have been shown in studies to promote a rapid heart rate (Steiner et al., 2002). According to one study, women are twice as likely as men to feel acute anxiety and stress (Remes et al., 2016). A study found that women are more vulnerable to stress when driving than men (Matthews et al., 1999). According to one study, women tend to react more emotionally because they have a completely distinct hormonal system (Seeman, 1997), and some of these gender differences occur throughout the reproductive years and gradually fade after menopause (Otte et al., 2005). As seen in Figures 2a and 2b, the human body reacts to stressful situations by releasing adrenaline, a hormone that causes the heart rate to accelerate. As a result, the hormonal system in women has a direct impact on the emotional state, influencing heart rate.

4.1.5. Types of roads

Figure 2e displays the declining heart rate trend for both techniques as the route shape changes from winding to monotonous. The findings revealed that road geometry factors had a significant impact on driving performance via influencing heart rate. When contrasted to a relatively difficult winding road, the heart rate drops during under-demanding monotonous driving. The monotonous highway stretches offer little geometric diversity, low traffic density and require less task effort, resulting in boredom and arousal fluctuations that reduce attentiveness and awareness. According to one study, the driver's attentiveness is significantly reduced due to the monotony of the route design and environment (Larue et al., 2011). A study found that driving on the expressway causes a motorist to feel weary faster, and the fatigue degree is significantly higher than driving on a high-demand country road for the same amount of time (Han et al., 2022). In such cases, the driver is more likely to feel passive tiredness symptoms, resulting in sleepy driving. A study that compared normal and sleepy driving indicated that the heart rate reduced dramatically in sleepy driving, from 855.6 bpm to 81.55.6 bpm (Jo et al., 2019). As a result, the physiological hallmark of boredom produced by a monotonous route influences heart rate.

4.2. Regression Model Validation

The regression model was validated to assess its accuracy in predicting significant input factors in influencing the output response, as well as how these factors influence each other in indicating driving fatigue, by comparing heart rate data acquired from software prediction and real-road driving experiments under the following conditions (Baluch et al., 2010):

- 1) The predicted interval of the output data generated through software prediction and real-road driving experiments must be within 90%. To forecast the value, the software created four polynomial equations, as shown in Table 3. The prediction value was obtained by substituting the original value of each independent variable determined in DOE into the equation.
- 2) The regression model is accurate if the residual error percentage is less than 10%.

Table 3: Polynomial equations generated by Design Expert software to predict heart rate data

Qualitative variable	Polynomial equations
Gender: Female Types of roads: Winding	Heart Rate = +159.54937 - 1.07290 * Age - 5.55226 * Driving Duration + 1.36762 * BMI - 5.77778E-003 * Age ² + 0.14027 * Driving Duration ² - 0.013611 * BMI ² + 2.42424E-003 * Age * Driving Duration + 0.017391 * Age * BMI - 3.95257E-003 * Driving Duration * BMI
Gender: Male Types of roads: Winding	Heart Rate = + 151.71506 - 1.10623 * Age - 5.44538 * Driving Duration + 1.32415 * BMI - 5.77778E-003 * Age ² + 0.14027 * Driving Duration ² - 0.013611 * BMI ² + 2.42424E-003 * Age * Driving Duration + 0.017391 * Age * BMI - 3.95257E-003 * Driving Duration * BMI
Gender: Female Types of roads: Monotonous	Heart Rate = +151.84084 - 1.03957 * Age - 5.43692 * Driving Duration + 1.28067 * BMI - 5.77778E-003 * Age ² + 0.14027 * Driving Duration ² - 0.013611 * BMI ² + 2.42424E-003 * Age * Driving Duration + 0.017391 * Age * BMI - 3.95257E-003 * Driving Duration * BMI
Gender: Male Types of roads: Monotonous	Heart Rate = +144.71241 - 1.07290 * Age - 5.33004 * Driving Duration + 1.23719 * BMI - 5.77778E-003 * Age ² + 0.14027 * Driving Duration ² - 0.013611 * BMI ² + 2.42424E-003 * Age * Driving Duration + 0.017391 * Age * BMI - 3.95257E-003 * Driving Duration * BMI

Table 4 shows three samples for data validation by comparing the accuracy of heart rate obtained by software prediction and real-road driving. Overall, the results suggest that all three samples meet the quantitative criterion for

reliably estimating heart rate. First, the model can assume the data inside a 95% prediction interval, meeting the minimum quantitative criterion of a 90% predictive interval. Second, the residual errors are less than 10%, indicating that the model is accurate in forecasting heart rate.

Table 4: Model validation (A= Age, B= Driving Duration, C= BMI, D= Gender and E= Road Types)

Run	Input parameter (Independent Variable)					Predict- ion	Real road	95% PI low	95% PI high	Error
	A	B	C	D	E	(bpm)	(bpm)	(bpm)	(bpm)	(%)
3	27.5	27.5	24.25	Female	Monotonous	109.29	112	105.5	113.1	2.71
20	27.5	27.5	24.25	Male	Winding	108.15	112	104.4	111.9	3.85
40	20.0	27.5	30.00	Female	Monotonous	120.0	121	115.8	124.2	1.02

5. Conclusion

The study aims to determine which factors, namely (i) age, (ii) driving duration, (iii) body mass index (BMI), (iv) gender and (v) types of roads are significant in affecting the heart rate and how these variables affect each other in indicating driving fatigue using regression analysis with Design Expert software. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was carried out by this software. The ANOVA findings reveal that the values of Prob>F for all input variables (A= Age, B= Driving Duration, C= BMI, D= Gender, and E= Road Types) are less than 0.01%, indicating that all factors have a substantial influence on the heart rate. Among the other variables, driving duration is the most significant. Because of the release of adrenaline in reaction to a stressful occurrence while driving, the heart rate decreases as age increases. The heart rate increases as the driving duration increases for the same reason. Meanwhile, the heart rate increases as BMI rises due to obesity-related health conditions. However, the heart rate reduces as gender shifts from female to male and road geometry shifts from winding to monotonous due to sex hormone differences and physiological signatures of boredom generated by road geometry respectively. The regression model's accuracy is determined by comparing output data from software prediction and real-world driving experiments. The model accurately forecasts the data within a 95% confidence interval, meeting the minimum quantitative constraint of a 90% confidence interval. Furthermore, the residual errors are fewer than 10%, implying that the model is reliable. The same methodology will be used in the next study to evaluate how cognitive skills like decision making and attention could indicate driving fatigue.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the Ministry of Higher Education (MOHE), for sponsoring this work under the Fundamental Research Grant Scheme (FRGS/1/2020/TK02/UTEM/02/5). Also, many thanks to the Faculty of Mechanical and Manufacturing in Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka.

References

- Foy, A. J., Mandrola, J., Liu, G., & Naccarelli, G. V. (2018). Relation of obesity to new-onset atrial fibrillation and atrial flutter in adults. *The American Journal of Cardiology*, 121(9), 1072-1075.
- Ani, M. F., Kamat, S. R., Hambali, R. H., & Mahmood, W. H. (2017). A study of psychophysical factor (heart rate) for driver fatigue using regression model. *Safety Health Environment*, 38(9), 1-9.
- Antoun, M., Edwards, K. M., Sweeting, J., & Ding, D. (2017). The acute physiological stress response to driving: A systematic review. *PLoS One*, 12(10), e0185517.
- Arnett, J. J. (2002). Developmental sources of crash risk in young drivers. *Injury Prevention*, 8(2), 17-23.
- Baluch, N. H., Abdullah, C. S., & Mohtar, S. (2010). Maintenance management performance—An overview towards evaluating Malaysian palm oil mill. *The Asian Journal of Technology Management*, 3(1), 1-5.
- Blair, M. L. (2007). Sex-based differences in physiology: what should we teach in the medical curriculum? *Advances in Physiology Education*, 31(1), 23-25.
- CEIC. (2021). *Malaysia Number of Registered Vehicles*. <https://www.ceicdata.com/en/indicator/malaysia/number-of-registered-vehicles#:~:text=Malaysia%20Number%20of%20Registered%20Vehicles%20was%20reported%20at%2017%2C486%2C589%20Unit,17%2C283%2C951%20Unit%20for%20Sep%202020>.

- Chua, E. C. P., Tan, W.Q., Yeo, S.C., Lau, P., Lee, I., Mien, I. H., & Gooley, J. J. (2012). Heart rate variability can be used to estimate sleepiness-related decrements in psychomotor vigilance during total sleep deprivation. *Sleep*, 35(3), 325-334.
- Clarke, D. D., Ward, P., Bartle, C., & Truman, W. (2010). Killer crashes: fatal road traffic accidents in the UK. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 42(2), 764-770.
- Di Milia, L., Smolensky, M. H., Costa, G., Howarth, H. D., Ohayon, M. M., & Philip, P. (2011). Demographic factors, fatigue, and driving accidents: An examination of the published literature. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 43(2), 516-532.
- Dobkin, P. L., & Pihl, R. O. (1992). Measurement of psychological and heart rate reactivity to stress in the real world. *Psychother Psychosom*, 58(3-4), 208-214. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000288629>
- Elagizi, A., Kachur, S., Lavie, C. J., Carbone, S., Pandey, A., Ortega, F. B., & Milani, R. V. (2018). An overview and update on obesity and the obesity paradox in cardiovascular diseases. *Progress in Cardiovascular Diseases*, 61(2), 142-150.
- Ferguson, S. A., Teoh, E. R., & McCartt, A. T. (2007). Progress in teenage crash risk during the last decade. *Journal of Safety Research*, 38(2), 137-145.
- Firdaus, M., Rahayu, R. S., & Husin, K. (2017). A study of psychophysical factor for driver fatigue using mathematical model. *Journal of Mechanical Engineering (JMEchE)*(2), 109-122.
- Frank, S., Colliver, J. A., & Frank, A. (1986, Feb). The electrocardiogram in obesity: statistical analysis of 1,029 patients. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 7(2), 295-299. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0735-1097\(86\)80494-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0735-1097(86)80494-6)
- Frewen, J., Finucane, C., & Kenny, R. A. (2013). Cognitive function is associated with impaired heart rate variability in ageing adults: the Irish longitudinal study on ageing wave one results. *Clinical Autonomic Research*, 23(6), 313-323.
- Gillie, B. L., Vasey, M. W., & Thayer, J. F. (2014). Heart rate variability predicts control over memory retrieval. *Psychological Science*, 25(2), 458-465.
- Han, H., Li, K., & Li, Y. (2022). Monitoring driving in a monotonous environment: classification and recognition of driving fatigue based on long short-term memory network. *Journal of Advanced Transportation*, 2022.
- Harms, C. A. (2006). Does gender affect pulmonary function and exercise capacity? *Respiratory Physiology & Neurobiology*, 151(2-3), 124-131.
- Haslam, D. W., & James, W. P. (2005, Oct 1). Obesity. *Lancet*, 366(9492), 1197-1209.
- Henelius, A., Sallinen, M., Huottilainen, M., Müller, K., Virkkala, J., & Puolamäki, K. (2014). Heart rate variability for evaluating vigilant attention in partial chronic sleep restriction. *Sleep*, 37(7), 1257-1267.
- Hidalgo-Muñoz, A. R., Mouratille., & El-Yagoubi, R. (2018). Cardiovascular correlates of emotional state, cognitive workload and time-on-task effect during a realistic flight simulation. *International Journal of Psychophysiology*, 128, 62-69.
- Ibrahim, M. S., Kamat, S. R., Shamsuddin, S., & Isa, M. H. M. (2022). Development of Driving Fatigue Strain Index using Fuzzy Logic to Quantify Impairment Risk Levels of Cognitive Skills in Vehicle Driving. *International Journal of Engineering Advanced Research*, 4(1), 121-139.
- Jo, S. H., Kim, J. M., & Kim, D. K. (2019). Heart rate change while drowsy driving. *Journal of Korean medical science*, 34(8).
- Kadoya, Y., Watanapongvanich, S., & Khan, M. S. R. (2021). How is emotion associated with driving speed? A study on taxi drivers in Japan. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology And Behaviour*, 79, 205-216.
- Larue, G. S., Rakotonirainy, A., & Pettitt, A. N. (2010). Predicting driver's hypovigilance on monotonous roads: literature review. 1st International Conference on Driver Distraction and Inattention,
- Larue, G. S., Rakotonirainy, A., & Pettitt, A. N. (2011). Driving performance impairments due to hypovigilance on monotonous roads. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 43(6), 2037-2046.
- Lavie, C. J., Arena, R., Alpert, M. A., Milani, R. V., & Ventura, H. O. (2018). Management of cardiovascular diseases in patients with obesity. *Nature Reviews Cardiology*, 15(1), 45-56.

- Leandro, M. (2012). Young drivers and speed selection: A model guided by the Theory of Planned Behavior. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology And Behaviour*, 15(3), 219-232.
- Legato, M. J., & Bilezikian, J. P. (2004). *Principles of gender-specific medicine* (Vol. 2). Gulf Professional Publishing.
- Leonhardt, S., Leicht, L., & Teichmann, D. (2018). Unobtrusive vital sign monitoring in automotive environments—A review. *Sensors*, 18(9), 3080.
- Li, K., Gong, Y., & Ren, Z. (2020). A fatigue driving detection algorithm based on facial multi-feature fusion. *IEEE Access*, 8, 101244-101259.
- Magaña, V. C., Scherz, W. D., Seepold, R., Madrid, N. M., Pañeda, X. G., & Garcia, R. (2020). The Effects of the Driver's Mental State and Passenger Compartment Conditions on Driving Performance and Driving Stress. *Sensors* 20(18).
- Matthews, G., Joyner, L., Gilliland, K., Campbell, S., Falconer, S., & Huggins, J. (1999). Validation of a comprehensive stress state questionnaire: Towards a state big three. *Personality Psychology In Europe*, 7, 335-350.
- May, J. F., & Baldwin, C. L. (2009). Driver fatigue: The importance of identifying causal factors of fatigue when considering detection and countermeasure technologies. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology And Be*, 12(3), 218-224.
- Milstead, R., Qin, X., Katz, B., Bonneson, J. A., Pratt, M., Miles, J., & Carlson, P. J. (2011). *Procedures For Setting Advisory Speeds On Curves*.
- MIROS. (2021). *Road Accidents and Fatalities in Malaysia* <https://www.mot.gov.my/en/land/safety/road-accident-and-facilities>
- Mohamad, F. (2017, 11/01). Do young Malaysian drivers involve in speeding behaviour: An investigation at selected accident hotspots in peninsular Malaysia.
- Otte, C., Hart, S., Neylan, T. C., Marmar, C. R., Yaffe, K., & Mohr, D. C. (2005). A meta-analysis of cortisol response to challenge in human aging: importance of gender. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 30(1), 80-91.
- Remes, O., Brayne, C., Van Der Linde, R., & Lafortune, L. (2016). A systematic review of reviews on the prevalence of anxiety disorders in adult populations. *Brain And Behavior*, 6(7), e00497.
- Rike, M. E., Diress, M., Dagneu, B., Getnet, M., Kebalo, A. H., Sinamaw, D., Solomon, D., & Akalu, Y. (2022). Hypertension and Its Associated Factors Among Long-Distance Truck Drivers in Ethiopia. *Integrated Blood Pressure Control*, 15, 67.
- Seeman, M. V. (1997). Psychopathology in women and men: focus on female hormones. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 154(12), 1641-1647.
- Sikander, G., & Anwar, S. (2018). Driver fatigue detection systems: A review. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 20(6), 2339-2352.
- Steiner, H., Ryst, E., Berkowitz, J., Gschwendt, M. A., & Koopman, C. (2002, Apr). Boys' and girls' responses to stress: affect and heart rate during a speech task. *Journal Adolesc Health*, 30(4 Suppl), 14-21.
- Steinhauser, K., Leist, F., Maier, K., Michel, V., Pärsch, N., Rigley, P., Wurm, F., & Steinhauser, M. (2018). Effects of emotions on driving behavior. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology And Behaviour*, 59, 150-163.
- Stelfox, H. T., Ahmed, S. B., Ribeiro, R. A., Gettings, E. M., Pomerantsev, E., & Schmidt, U. (2006). Hemodynamic monitoring in obese patients: the impact of body mass index on cardiac output and stroke volume. *Critical Care Medicine*, 34(4), 1243-1246.
- Wang, H., Cao, J., Li, J., Chen, J., Wu, X., Duan, X., Huang, J., & Gu, D. (2010, 2010/04/12). Blood pressure, body mass index and risk of cardiovascular disease in Chinese men and women. *BMC Public Health*, 10(1), 189.
- Yotsutsuji, H., Kita, H., Xing, J., & Hirai, S. (2017). A car-accident rate index for curved roads: A speed choice-based approach. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 25, 2108-2118.
- Zhao, Y., Yamamoto, T., & Kanamori, R. (2020, 2020/08/01/). Study of older male drivers' driving stress compared with that of young male drivers. *Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering (English Edition)*, 7(4), 467-481.